

Customer Preference of Organized versus Traditional Retail Stores in India: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

Retail sector expanding with fastest rate in India. Total retail sector is growing at a much faster rate of 45-50% per annum. From which, organized retail reported 16% for the year 2011-12. At the same time traditional retail formats have predominately covered the market. Now, the retail formats are operating with more sophistication in order to provide a new and distinct experience. The Modern retail stores are providing now a new shopping experience to customers and constantly providing a wide range of choice.

In order to know how the modern formats appeals to consumers on different dimensions or parameters various studies were carried out. In the literature the relationship between store attributes and preference for retail format is also examined. This study focuses on, why consumers prefer a modern retail store in comparison with a traditional retail store.

Keywords:

Retail Formats, Customer Preference, Organized Retailing, Traditional Retailing

Introduction

Retail sector expanding with fastest rate in India. Total retail sector is growing at a much faster rate of 45-50% per annum. From which, organized retail reported 16% for the year 2011-12. At the same time traditional retail formats have predominately covered the market. Now, the retail formats are operating with more sophistication in order to provide a new and distinct experience. The Modern retail stores are providing now a new shopping experience to customers and constantly providing a wide range of choice. The modern formats appeals to the consumers on different dimensions or parameters. However, in the literature the relationship between store attributes and preference for retail format is also examined. There are few past studies, for example, Arnold (1997) and Sparks (1995) have shown in their research work that pricing, product assortment, and customer services are important factors in determining choice of format in the department store context. In addition, according to Baker et al. (1994) and Donovan et al. (1994) mentioned that store environment and atmosphere appear to be influential in consumers' preferred format decisions. The findings of studies published in the trade literature like Chain Store Age (2004) and Taylor (2003) are similar, identifying product assortment, availability, convenience, and pricing as significant drivers of format preference. Therefore consumers prefer to visit on one of or some of those parameters.

Hence, it becomes very important for organized retailers to know that on which parameters consumers prefer organized retail store than traditional store for shopping.

Research Objectives and Methodology

The basic objective of this study is to identify the customer preference parameters for selection of retail stores. It aims to identify the preference parameters for shopping at organized retail stores rather than traditional stores. For this study, an exploratory research design was considered appropriate. The information was collected through a sample survey. Data were collected from the consumers visiting Big Bazaar, D-Mart, Reliance Mart, and Vishal Mega Mart in four major cities of Gujarat state (Ahmedabad, Vadodara, Surat, and Rajkot). Researchers have drawn the samples applying convenience sampling procedure. The sample size was determined applying proportions (determining the sample size when estimating proportions). Considering confidence level of 95 per cent, a margin of sampling error (or precision) of ± 5 per cent, and proportion of a sample for the survey is shown in the following table. Thus, the final sample size was calculated to be 955. Thus, the study attempted to attain sample reliability within ± 5 per cent margin of error at the 95 per cent confidence level.

Table 2.1 Determination of Sample Size

City	p ^a	q ^b	p*q	SSE ^c	Std. Value	p*q/SSE	Sample Size (n)
Ahmedabad	0.85	0.15	0.128	0.0025	3.8416	0.000650771	196
Vadodara	0.82	0.18	0.148	0.0025	3.8416	0.000650771	227
Surat	0.81	0.19	0.154	0.0025	3.8416	0.000650771	236
Rajkot	0.74	0.26	0.192	0.0025	3.8416	0.000650771	296
Total Sample Size							955
a. Probability							
b. 1 - Probability							
c. Square of sampling error							

The secondary data was collected from journals, magazines, reports, research studies, government publications, professional publications, research organizations and websites.

A survey approach was chosen in order to collect data directly from consumers visiting the identified organized retail stores operating in the city of selected cities. A survey methodology permits the use of questions to measure constructs exclusively internal to respondents, e.g. perceptions, attitudes, opinions, intentions, etc., (Cooper and Schindler, 1998), and the answers can be collected and combined to represent the answers of an entire population (Reaves, 1992). At an exit door (store intercept manner) was conducted at storefront with consumers who were asked to fill the questionnaire, used by Rani and Velayudhan (2008) in their study. For the purpose of computing statistical accuracy researchers applied one sample Binomial Test and Percentage & Frequency Analysis. From the calculated outcomes meaningful interpretations were drawn for the organized retail sector.

Literature Review

Proximity of Location: Store preference is regarded as a cognitive process and one of the influential factors for the preference of a store is store location. Therefore, at the time of making choice of shopping place consumers assign due importance to the location of a retail store. A study carried out by Baltas and Papastathopoulou (2003) identified store location as a key driver for the choice of a retail store. As pointed out by Kahn and Schmittlein (1989), that store choice has also been found dependent on the timing of shopping trips as consumers may go to a local store (having close proximity of location) for short “fill-in” trips and to a more distant store for regular shopping trips.

Parking: Consumers mostly visit the retail store by their personal vehicle, often by two-wheeler or a car in India. Newman and Cullen (2002) mentioned that consumers require plenty of free parking nearby store with adequately spaced places for easier parking. It was further identified that poor and costly parking

services also influence the consumers for their preference to shop at the particular retail store.

Range of Products: The most important element of the retail mix is the range of products offered to consumers, which in turn help retailers to make a consumers’ preferred retail store. A study undertaken by Hansen and Solgaard (2004) provides several important findings relevant to merchandise. Product assortment (range of products) was identified as the single most influential variable affecting the preference for retail format. In addition, similar results were produced in a research done by Baltas and Papastathopoulou (2003) where product assortment was one of the key drivers of preference for the kind of a retail store.

Price: The consumers’ preference for a particular shopping place is based on the price of the merchandise. According to Sheikh and Fatima (2008), price is perceived as one of the important element in the consumers’ purchase decision and therefore it impacts the store choice decision of them. It is also supported by Bajaj et. al. (2005) that from consumers’ perspective, price is considered always a significant parameter in the purchase decision of a product which in turn influences the store preference decision of consumers.

Time Taken for Billing: Today consumers are found with less or no time and hence time taken for billing becomes an essential attribute of the retail store. As mentioned in one of the report published by Orizin Technologies (n.d), long queue at the billing section is one of the most common scenarios visible today at all the retail stores. It was further mentioned that currently the systems installed cannot read multiple items together at the time of billing leading to long queues in front of the billing counter and hence wastage of customer’s precious time. Kushwaha (December/2009) shared that consumers are convinced by all the store attributes but there are still some problems in retail stores, to begin with lots of time are wasted in billing even in festive season and in

weekdays shopping time are much less than billing time. So, it is posits as under.

Noninterference: Today consumers are much confident and it is proposed that consumers are predetermined about their shopping. They do not consider any other's opinion. Such consumers do not seek any guidance it is regarded as needless interference. Explaining the same issue, Prus (1993) quoted that while consumers are typically envisioned to be skeptical of the retailer they encounter in their shopping ventures. Therefore, noninterference becomes one of the most important parameter for store preference.

Courtesy of Employees: The behavior of employees upon store choice has relevance. Employees' politeness and the interest shown in helping the consumer make his/her decision are important determinants of a store's preference for shopping, as highlighted by Armistead and Kiely (2003). Fram and Axelrod (1990) explained that courtesy of employees while providing information on product quality is even more important when consumers are buying expensive goods such as electrical appliances. It is reasonable then to assume that employees' behavior influence the preference for the store format.

Discount Offers: Discount offers remain home to plenty of consumer spending. But discount offers should be designed more nimbly to track fickle customer preferences. According to Varley and Rafiq (2004), discount offers stimulate consumers for the limited period of time to stimulate trial or increase in sales. The economic shoppers always take advantage of such discounts and hence it becomes the preference parameter of the store choice for the consumers. So, researcher posits.

Accuracy of Weights: Based on the researcher's discussion with the consumers with respect to accuracy of weights, it was identified that weights might not be accurate at the traditional retail stores especially in case of fruits and loose items. Therefore, researcher has tested here whether consumers prefer organized retail store or traditions retail store based accuracy of weights.

Ambience of the Store: The role of ambience in store choice has also been found significant. Kotler (1973) has proposed atmospherics as an important parameter considered by consumers while visiting retail store. It is also found that the shoppers determine to buy the merchandise based on non-monetary costs including the store atmosphere, noted by Zeithaml (1988). Treblanche (1999) found that ambience (a non-monetary value) was the major driver for visiting a retail store. The shopping experience, as created by the store environment, has been found to play an important role in building store patronage and making it a proffered shopping place for consumers.

Home Delivery: The traditional retailers are ubiquitous and they already offer a very convenient home delivery service in India. Rangaswamy (September/2007) reported that the traditional retailers (mom and pop stores) will dominate the grocery home delivery segment of the Indian retail market. In addition to this, he further mentioned that large retailers, like Reliance Fresh, Trinetra, Spencer Daily, Big Bazaar will not be able to match this home delivery service. It was also reported by him that in the US and Europe the results on home delivery has been mixed. Webvan, Home Grocer, Streamline all folded up. However, Sainsburys, Safeway and Tesco are continuing with the home delivery service. In India Unilever's Sangam Direct and Fabmart's home delivery grocery have closed now.

Personal Consideration: Li J. et. al. (2009) opined that for retailers, a rich and engaging in-store customer shopping experience is a key to become a proffered shopping store for customers and increasing the value of customers' shopping baskets. Santosh (2009) cited that big format have the benefit of economies of scale, hence can give huge discount & provide huge varieties. But the sheer number of footfalls makes it very difficult to provide personalized services. Small formats operating on lower customer base should focus on forging personal relationships. Wadhwa (2009) mentioned that establishing customer relationship by providing great shopping experience through personalized service ensures customer loyalty is an important store part of shopping experience.

Data Analysis and Results

For the purpose of analysis and finding the preferred store on particular parameter, the researchers have

organized data in the frequency and percentage of consumers through frequency distribution table as under.

Table: 1: Consumers' Preference for Organized or Traditional Retail Store vs. Comparison Parameters

N=955 Comparison Parameters	Organized Retail Store (Modern Store)		Traditional Store (Conventional Store)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Proximity of Location	750	78.5	205	21.5
Parking	845	88.5	110	11.5
Range of products	853	89.3	102	10.7
Price	751	78.6	204	21.4
Time taken for billing	476	49.8	479	50.2
Noninterference	640	67.0	315	33.0
Courtesy of employees	849	88.9	106	11.1
Discounts offers	875	91.6	80	8.4
Accuracy of weights	830	86.9	125	13.1
Personal consideration	440	46.1	515	53.9
Home delivery	439	46.0	516	54.0
Ambience of the store	854	89.4	101	10.6

The frequency distribution table (Table 5.20) shows that majority of the consumers prefer the organized retail stores than the traditional retail stores on the basis of the identified comparative parameters namely, proximity of location, parking, range of products, price, noninterference, courtesy of employees, accuracy of weights. Whereas around 50% of the consumers prefer both the organized retail stores and the traditional

retail stores on the basis of the identified comparative parameters namely, time taken for billing, personal consideration, home delivery.

H1: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on proximity of location.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Proximity of Location	Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	
Group 1	Organized Retail Store	750	.79	.50	.000 ^a	
Group 2	Traditional Store	205	.21			
Total		955	1.00			

a. Based on Z Approximation.

The binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) is 0.000, where the test proportion value is 50%. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is obvious that there is significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on proximity of

location. At the same time the observed proportions value suggests majority of the consumers (79%) give preference to organized retail store based on the proximity of location. Thus, it may be concluded that majority of the consumers prefer organized retail store based on proximity of location.

H2: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference

of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on parking.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Parking		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Organized Retail Store	845	.88	.50	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Traditional Store	110	.12		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

With the test proportion value of 50%, the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) comes 0.000. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected and it can be noticed that there is significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on parking. On the contrary, the observed proportions value indicates majority of the consumers (88%) give preference to organized retail store based on the

price. Hence the analysis suggests that majority of the consumers prefer organized retail store based on parking.

H3: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on range of products.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Range of Products		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Traditional Store	102	.11	.50	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Organized Retail Store	853	.89		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

Here, the null hypothesis is rejected as the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) is 0.000, with test proportion value of 50%. Hence, there is significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on range of products. In fact the observed proportions value implicates majority of the consumers (89%) give preference to

organized retail store based on the range of products. Thus, it is clear that mostly all the consumers prefer organized retail store based on range of products.

H4: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on price.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Price		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Organized Retail Store	751	.79	.50	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Traditional Store	204	.21		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

Here the observed proportions value suggests majority of the consumers (79%) give preference to organized retail store based on the price. Though the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) is 0.000, considering the test proportion is 50%. Hence the hypothesis is rejected, so it is obvious that there is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on price. Hence,

organized retail store is a preferred shopping place for majority of consumers.

H4: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on time taken for billing.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Time taken for billing		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Traditional Store	479	.50	.50	.948 ^a
	Group 2	Organized Retail Store	476	.50		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

In case of consumers' preference for organized retail store or traditional retail store, the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) is 0.948 which is almost near to one, keeping the test proportion value as 50%. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and it is much obvious that there is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on time taken for billing. This suggests 50% of

consumers prefer organized retail store and 50% of consumers prefer traditional retail store based on time taken for billing.

H5: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on noninterference.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Non-Interference		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Organized Retail Store	640	.67	.50	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Traditional Store	315	.33		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

The binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) is 0.000, where the test proportion is 50%. Hence the hypothesis is rejected, hence it can be noticed that there is significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on noninterference. Considering the observed proportions value, it is inferred that more than of the consumers (67%) give preference to organized retail store based on

the non-interference. Thus it is clear that majority of consumers prefer organized retail store based on non-interference.

H6: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on courtesy of employees.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Courtesy of employees		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Traditional Store	106	.11	.50	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Organized Retail Store	849	.89		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

In case of courtesy of employees, keeping the test proportion value of 50%, the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) comes 0.000. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and therefore, there is significant difference among consumers' preference for organized retail store and traditional retail store based on courtesy of employees. On the contrary, the observed proportions value indicates majority of the consumers (89%) give preference to organized retail

store based on the courtesy of employees. Therefore, it is evident that majority of the consumers prefer organized retail store based on courtesy of employees.

H7: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on discounts offers.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Discounts offers		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Organized Retail Store	875	.92	.50	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Traditional Store	80	.08		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

The binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) is 0.000, where the test proportion is 50%. Hence the hypothesis is rejected, hence it is obvious that there is significant difference among consumers' preference for organized retail store and traditional retail store based on discount offers. At the same time the observed proportions suggests majority of the consumers (92%) give preference to organized retail store based on the

discount offers. This suggests, organized retailers that almost all the consumers prefer organized retail store based on discounts offers.

H8: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on accuracy of weights.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Accuracy of weights		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Traditional Store	125	.13	.50	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Organized Retail Store	830	.87		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

Here the observed proportions value suggests majority of the consumers (87%) prefer to organized retail store based on the accuracy of weights. Though the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) is 0.000, keeping the test proportion is 50%. Hence the hypothesis is rejected, thus it is clear that there is significant difference among consumers' preference for organized retail store and traditional retail store

based on accuracy of weights. From this analysis it is evident that majority of the consumers prefer organized retail store based on accuracy of weight.

H9: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on the accuracy of weights.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Ambience of the store		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Organized Retail Store	854	.89	.50	.000 ^a
	Group 2	Traditional Store	101	.11		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

With the test proportion value of 50%, the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) comes 0.000. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected and it is inferred that there is significant difference among consumers' preference for organized retail store and traditional retail store based on ambience of store. At the same time the observed proportions value suggests majority of the consumers (89%) give preference to organized retail store based on the ambience of store.

So, it can be concluded that majority of the consumers prefer organized retail store based on ambience of the store.

H10: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on home delivery.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Home delivery		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Traditional Store	516	.54	.50	.014 ^a
	Group 2	Organized Retail Store	439	.46		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

For the home delivery, considering the test proportion value of 50%, the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) comes 0.014. So, the null hypothesis can be accepted at lower level and therefore it can be concluded that there is no significant difference among consumers' preference for organized retail store and traditional retail store based on courtesy of employees. However, the observed proportions value shows 46% of the consumers prefer organized retail

store based on the home delivery. This suggests that almost equal number (50%) of consumers prefer both organized retail store and traditional retail store based on home delivery.

H11: There is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on personal consideration.

Binomial Test						
Preference based on Personal consideration		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
	Group 1	Organized Retail Store	440	.46	.50	.017 ^a
	Group 2	Traditional Store	515	.54		
	Total		955	1.00		

a. Based on Z Approximation.

Based on personal consideration, the binomial test significant value (for the two tailed test) comes 0.017, taking the test proportion value of 50%. Hence, the null hypothesis may be accepted at lower level and thus it can be concluded that there is no significant difference among consumers' preference for organized retail store and traditional retail store based on based on personal consideration. From the observed proportions value it is clear that 46% of the consumers give preference to organized retail store based on the personal consideration. Hence it is clear that based on personal consideration, roughly equal number (50%) of consumers prefer organized retail store and traditional retail store.

Conclusion:

From the survey findings it is surmised that majority of the consumers prefer to buy grocery, vegetables, cosmetics & beauty products, and clothes/apparels from the organized retail stores, the percentage of consumers prefer to buy grocery, vegetables, cosmetics & beauty products, and clothes/apparels from the organized retail stores. On the contrary, most of the consumers prefer to buy gift articles, toys, fabric care products, oral care products, stationery, medicines, electronics items, and books & CDs from the traditional/any other retail stores. Whereas around equal number of the consumers have shown the preference to buy cutlery, footwear, furniture, and food products from either the organized retail stores or traditional/any other retail stores.

The primary research disclosed that there is significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on proximity of location, parking, range of

products, price, noninterference, courtesy of employees, discount offers, accuracy of weights, accuracy of weights and majority of consumers prefer organized retail stores on the basis of the above store preference parameters.

According to survey results, there is no significant difference in the proportions of consumers for the preference of organized retail store and traditional retail store based on time taken for billing, home delivery, and personal consideration as for these parameters almost equal proportion (half) of consumers preferred both organized retail store and traditional retail store.

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